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On the nature of the new social contract and COVID-19 mortality, cases, and ICUs

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Dear editor, more than one year ago, your journal published [1] a cryptic letter introducing of the need for a new social contract (NSC) because of the COVID-19 pandemic. The nature of this contract, which the authors refer to as evidence-based contract, remains obscure to me. It seems that the common practice in this NSC is to cherry pick the data that provides the desired evidence for goals set *a priori*. For the interested reader, the accompanying figure [2] shows some data and straightforward statistical analysis that may rise relevant questions to the mass “vaccination” strategy imposed by the financial interests that are clearly reflected in part **D** of the figure. Note in part **A** that the lowest deaths, cases and ICU patients in Israel happen at the time when the “vaccine” loses effect and the next dose is mandated by the pharmaceuticals. Instead of being evidence based, the NSC is financially beneficial for some stakeholders that have reaped huge profits for a product of dubious quality. The “vaccination” did not reduce significantly COVID-19 mortality, cases or ICU patients. To understand this NSC and the implications for the general population, Industry 4.0 is a convenient framework where products are continuously evolving, so that the user is a guinea pig that contributes to their improvement by experimenting and providing data. Hence, the user is forever dependent of the provider, and it is working for its benefit. Under this NSC the general public is working for the improvement of the pharmaceutical product, without the benefit of a proper follow up, because by definition adverse effects do not exist. Moreover, the users have become disposable paying guinea pigs that receive a standard product “good for all sizes” and need not to be taken care of. Users will be happy and will own nothing, i.e. they will not own their bodies and their functionality that is put to the service of the development of the medical product. It appears to me that the NSC is a turning point for medical science and practice. Instead of servicing the patient, the NSC asks the patient to be at the service of the industry. That the medical strategy is dictated by the industry has become self-evident. One can even wonder, according to the data in the figure, if the pharmaceutical intervention is in fact sustaining the pandemic dynamics.

References

- [1] Atlani-Duault L, Lina B, Chauvin F, Delfraissy JF, Malvy D Immune evasion means we need a new COVID-19 social contract. *Lancet Public Health*. 2021; 6: e199-e200
- [2] Manuel Graña. (2022). A Letter to Lancet: On the nature of the new social contract and COVID mortality, cases, and ICUs. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6376777>

Figure caption: **A** contains screenshots from ourworldindata.org (OWID) showing the deaths (**A1**), cases (**A2**), and ICU patients (**A3**). Red bars mark the beginning of first doses, boosters and 4th doses. Light Green arrows point of minimal deaths, cases, and ICU patients, which happen when the vaccines have lost effectiveness. **B** plots the p-value of non-parametric left ranksum test comparing the deaths (**B1**), cases (**B2**), and ICU patients (**B3**) before and after (Alternative hypothesis: After > Before) the beginning of the vaccination, considering all countries in OWID and symmetric time periods around the beginning of the vaccination. It can be appreciated that the vaccination does not contribute significantly to reduce any of the measures, at any time. **C** contains the same plots around the beginning of the booster doses, with similar conclusions. **D** contains screenshots of the stock 5 year history of some relevant vaccination stakeholders.